

AUTOMATED SYSTEM OF QUALITY CONTROL OF TECHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF REPAIR OF WHEEL PAIRS.

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Annotation: This article covers the automation of wheel repair. in this text, increasing labor productivity in the repair of a pair of wheels, in addition, the requirements for the control system are highlighted.

Key words : management systems ; technological process; flexibility in system; subsystems; technological devices.

In order to implement the targeted technological process, it is necessary to control and manage it. As for the considered technological process of repairing wheel pairs, this means that at all stages of production it is necessary to constantly monitor the parameters of the repair process, the completeness and quality of control-measurement, diagnostic and repair work. in relation to units (parts) during the repair period to ensure the guaranteed production of products of a certain quality.

Increasing labor productivity and product quality in any production management systems largely depends on their technical equipment, which determines the functional capabilities of these systems. The main task of the control system is to integrate technological workplaces into a single information and control space, regardless of the number and range of incoming components and parts, using standard computing tools. Information about the nature of the work performed simultaneously in these workplaces and the obtained parameters should come directly to the technological devices with the repair objects.

The system should allow you to automatically determine all the details and all the technological operations that must be performed to fully restore the repair object

or ensure its working condition. In this case, the system should transfer the processing (repair) program of the incoming parts directly to the technological devices. In addition, after carrying out a certain technological operation, after receiving a unit (part) from the workplace and remembering all its parameters and the amount of work performed, the system can provide information at the stage of moving the repair object to the next stage. must provide. Such movement of components and parts and their maintenance should be carried out under the control of the computer system until the end of the specified technological cycle. In some cases, the system must also work offline from the management controllers that are part of the developed identification and coding system.

The following were considered as requirements for the management system:

- ASC hierarchy level;
- justification of the number of measured (monitored) parameters, as well as the correctness of their compliance with the monitored values;
- functions to be performed (single-cycle or multi-link automatic control, static and or dynamic optimization, optimal control);
- connecting technical means of the system with technological and control-measuring equipment;
- Prospects for the development and modernization of ASC.

The results of research and modeling of the object of control - the technological and logical process of repair made it possible to formulate functional tasks for monitoring compliance with the requirements for technological discipline and ASC elements, which include:

- taking into account operational-statistical indicators of the quality and quantity indicators of manufactured products with the specified accuracy within the specified limits;
- the possibility of operational centralized control of all effects on the repair object during the repair period;

flexibility in system management - rapid transition from automatic data entry in a closed loop with a computer to autonomous - semi-automatic or manual and vice versa, when repair is combined with control, measurement and technological equipment of production.

At the same time, in any mode, the system must ensure the stability of the following key indicators:

- quantitative - the time of operations for each repair object, the overall productivity of technological operations and the ratios of the total finished product production site;

- quality - indicators that determine the generality of properties and properties that determine the suitability of the finished product for its intended use.

In addition, the system should be highly reliable, convenient and easy to use.

The breakdown of the technological process of repair of wheel pairs and their units (parts) and evaluation of production preparation allows to distinguish two main subsystems from its general structure:

- accepting a pair of wheels for repair with a guaranteed level of detection of defects and determining the type of necessary repair;

- control of all parts and assembly units during the repair process, guaranteeing the elimination of detected defects.

These subsystems ensure the fulfillment of a number of mandatory technological requirements for the system's operating modes, compliance with the most important technical.

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